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OGRANIČENJE PRAVA DETETA NA SAZNAJJE POREKLA

Pravo deteta da zna svoje poreklo predstavlja jedno od osnovnih prava priznatih Konvencijom o pravima deteta, kao sastavni deo šireg prava na očuvanje identiteta (čl. 8). Ovo pravo je inkorporirano i u ustavnopravni i zakonodavni okvir Republike Srbije, naročito u Porodični zakon. U praksi se, međutim, pravo deteta na saznanje porekla najčešće poistovećuje sa pravom na poznavanje biološkog porekla, što je posledica naučnog napretka u oblasti genetike i orijentacije ka „genetskoj istini“. Takav pristup, prihvaćen i u praksi Evropskog suda za ljudska prava, ponekad dovodi do kolizije između genetske realnosti i potrebe očuvanja stabilnosti porodičnih odnosa. Konvencijska odredba da dete ima ovo pravo „ako je to moguće“ implicira postojanje i faktičkih i pravnih ograničenja ovog prava. U pravu Republike Srbije, ona su najčešće prisutna u slučajevima biomedicinski potpomognute oplodnje i opravdavaju se zaštitom najboljeg interesa deteta, koje mora imati prioritetan karakter, što se pokazuje i u najnovijoj sudskoj praksi u RS. Razlikuju se direktna ograničenja, kada sud ograničava primenu genetske ekspertize radi očuvanja porodične stabilnosti i prava uključenih lica, vodeći računa o društvenim okolnostima u kojima dete živi. Na ovaj način se poreklo štiti od njegove biologizacije, ali i afirmišu porodične vrednosti. Indirektna ograničenja proizilaze iz procesnih pravila o licima ovlašćenim za pokretanje postupka i rokovima za podnošenje tužbe u parnicama za utvrđivanje porekla deteta. Cilj svih ovih ograničenja jeste uspostavljanje pravične ravnoteže između biološkog i društvenog aspekta roditeljstva, kako bi se obezbedio primat najboljeg interesa deteta.

Ključne reči: pravo deteta na saznanje porekla; biološko poreklo; najbolji interes deteta; ograničenja prava; biomedicinska oplodnja.

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RESTRICTION OF THE CHILD'S RIGHT TO KNOW HIS/HER ORIGIN

The right of the child to know his/her origin is one of the basic rights acknowledged by the CoE Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989), as a constituent part of the broader right of the child to preserve his/her identity (Article 8 CRC). This right is incorporated into the constitutional and legislative framework of the Republic of Serbia, particularly in the Family Act. In practice, however, the right of the child to know his/her origin is often equated with the right to know one's biological origin, which is the consequence of scientific developments in the field of genetics and the orientation towards "genetic truth". Such an approach, which has been accepted in the judicial practice of the European Court of Human Rights, sometimes leads to a collision between the genetic reality and the need to maintain the stability of family relations. The Convention provision stating that the child is entitled to this right "as far as possible" implies the existence of factual and legal restrictions of this right.

In Serbian law, these restrictions are most prominent in cases of biomedically assisted reproduction, and are justified by the best interest of the child that must have priority. This stance has been accepted by and exemplified in the latest Serbian court practice. Yet, there is a distinction between direct and indirect restrictions. Direct restrictions entail the court's decision to restrict the use of genetic expertise in order to maintain the stability of family relations and protect the rights of the parties involved, taking into account the social circumstances of the child's immediate living environment. In this way, the child's origin is protected from its biologization and the family values are affirmed. Indirect restrictions are based on procedural rules referring to the persons who are eligible to initiate the procedure and the statute of limitations (time limits) for filing complaints in lawsuits for determining the child's origin. The goal of all these restrictions is to find a right balance between the biological and social aspects of parenthood in order to insure the supremacy of the best interest of the child.

Keywords: the right of the child to know his/her origin, biological origin, the best interest of the child, restrictions, biomedical reproduction.